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Abstract book

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SBRT without HT is a validated option for low and favorable intermediate risk prostate cancer – YES

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Background: Stereotactic Body Radiation Therapy (SBRT) is increasingly used to treat metastatic prostate cancer, especially for oligometastatic disease (OMD). Based on available data, OMD can to date be defined as 1-5 metastatic lesions, a controlled primary tumor being optional, but where all metastatic sites must be safely treatable. SBRT delivers high doses of radiation with precision, minimizing damage to surrounding healthy tissues. It can be targeting the primary tumor as well the metastatic sites. SBRT is also used in localized low risk) prostate cancer. Definition of low and favorable intermediate risk prostate cancer. Low risk: Tumor is confined to the prostate, and the PSA is <10 and grade group 1 (Gleason 6). There is also a subset of extremely “slow-growing” tumors called “very low risk” in which fewer than 3 biopsy tissue samples contain cancer cells and the cancer is not detectable by DRE. Favorable intermediate-risk prostate cancer includes patients with <50% positive biopsy cores and one intermediate-risk feature: a T2b-c tumor, a pathological Gleason score (GS) of 3 + 4 = 7 (grade group 2), or serum prostate-specific antigen (PSA) of 10–20 ng/ml.

SBRT Alone: Based on the current available literature, the GETUG group suggests that: 1. Because large prospective trials are lacking, SBRT could not be considered as a standard of care, but could be proposed as an option after patient information; 2. Good candidates for SBRT are patients of the favorable or intermediate favorable groups.

For oligometastatic prostate cancer, SBRT has been shown to control local disease and delay the progression of metastatic lesions, potentially prolonging survival. The key advantages of SBRT alone include: 1. High precision and effectiveness in targeting small metastatic lesions; 2. Minimal side effects; 3. SBRT requires fewer sessions (usually 1 to 5 treatments) compared to traditional radiation therapy; 4. Delay in the need for more systemic treatments, such as chemotherapy or hormonal therapy. SBRT

alone is more common in patients with a limited number of metastases and slower-growing cancer.

Conclusion: The choice between SBRT alone or in combination with chemotherapy depends on the extent and aggressiveness of the metastatic disease, as well as patient-specific factors like overall health and preferences. Consultation with a multidisciplinary Team-Tumor board (including radiation oncologists, medical oncologists, and urologists) is essential to tailor the best treatment approach.

Keywords: Prostate cancer, SBRT

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